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**MASTER'S PHOTO ART PROJECT
'EROTICA IN PHOTOGRAPHY:
FROM ANALOG TO DIGITAL'. PART 1****Volodymyr Kukorenchuk^{1a}, Nataliia Vdovychenko^{2a}, Valeriia Bondar^{3a}**

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**МАГІСТЕРСЬКИЙ ФОТОМИСТЕЦЬКИЙ ПРОЄКТ
«ЕРОТИКА У ФОТОГРАФІЇ:
ВІД АНАЛОГА ДО ЦИФРИ». ЧАСТИНА 1****Володимир Кукоренчук^{1a}, Наталія Вдовиченко^{2a}, Валерія Бондар^{3a}**

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The author's idea. The idea of this Master's Photo Art Project was to create an erotic photographic work, namely such images that contain elements of fine art, which are closely intertwined with the myths and legends of ancient Greece. Throughout photographic history, both historical aspects and stylistic images of the visual art of each era are explored and intersect.

The photographic project is based on the story of characters such as Eros, three graces – Innocence, Beauty and Love. During the development of the storyline, the characters go through the ages, their aesthetics and expressiveness. The passage of time and the development of society in terms of morality change the attitude toward the naked human body and its interpretation.

The analysis of beauty of a human body in various forms of sensuality is carried out. It is established that eroticism is the result of the process of ontogenetic, cultural development and expresses the individual psychological and semantic components of the uniqueness of the human body. And photography, as the most common way of visual communication, has formed modern ideas about it.

Photo No. 1

**“Birth of Eros” of the Master’s Photo Art Project
“Erotica in Photography: from Analog to Digital”**

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Camera / Lens

Fujifilm XT-3 /
Fujinon XF 35 mm f/2.0

Settings:

35 mm | F2.8 | ISO 400 | 1/60 s

**Image No. 1 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

Increase exposure, decrease saturation,
zoom based on content, overlay photos
on top of each other.

Light scheme

Three lighting devices were used
for the shooting. The painting light was
located to the left of the model. The fill light
was near the optical axis of the camera.
Contrast – top behind the model.

Author's idea of photo №1. Photo №1 “Birth of Eros” shows one of the main characters of this photographic work. Proponents of Orphic cosmogony believed that the god Eros was born from an egg laid by Nyukta (or created by Chronos). This legend gave impetus to the creation of just such a plot image that inspires a sense of originality.

To realize this idea, I turned to the works of photographers and artists of the nineteenth century. I was inspired by David Octavius Hill, Robert Adamson, Charles Negre, Roger Fenton, Henry Fox Talbot and François Pascal Simon Gérard, Francisco Goya, Antoine-Jean Gros and others.

This photo is fully consistent with the style of the Classicism era – the expressiveness of form, specificity of the image and the proportions.

To create such an image, we used two digital photos that were compiled in Adobe Photoshop and superimposed on each other. The shooting was carried out in the photo pavilion using special equipment. As a result of many attempts, I settled on a light tonal image of the image in a high key.

Translucent fabric was thrown on the model for a more expressive effect. Light and form create a sense of unity.

Photo No. 2

**“Fascination with Graces” of the Master’s Photo Art Project
“Erotica in Photography: from Analog to Digital”**

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Camera / Lens

Canon 60D /
Canon 24-105 f/4L IS II USM

Settings:

24 mm | F4.5 | ISO 250 | 1/10 s

**Image No. 2 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

Increase exposure, decrease saturation, zoom based on content, overlay photos, reduce opacity, motion blur.

Light scheme

Three lighting devices were used for the shooting. The painting light was located to the left of the model. The fill light was near the optical axis of the camera. Contrast – top behind the model.

Author's idea of photo №2. At the photo №2 "Admiration of Graces" not only Eros is involved, but also three Graces – Innocence, Beauty and Love. These heroines also came from the ancient Greek epic and were sung by the Great Masters of Fine Arts throughout the civilized history of mankind.

I decided to add these characters to the story of Eros to emphasize his incipience as a god of love. At the photo, Graces enchant Eros with their seductive dance. They have captivated his soul so much that he wants to take possession of them and never let them go. This is where the story of temptation begins.

This photo corresponds to the style of the Romantic era – the spiritual world of man comes to the fore, creating a whole with nature.

To create such an image, I have used 8 photos and a scanned herbarium, which were compiled in the Adobe Photoshop editor and superimposed on each other. The shooting was carried out in the photo pavilion with the use of special equipment, and the light-tone drawing of the image in a high key became the best solution for the realization of this idea.

The use of props for this photo was similar to the previous one.

Photo No. 3

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**"Temptation" of the Master's Photo Art Project
"Erotica in Photography: from Analog to Digital"**

Camera / Lens

Fujifilm XT-3 /
Fujinon XF 35 mm f/2.0

Settings:

35 mm | F2.8 | ISO 80 | 1/30 s

**Image No. 3 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

Increase exposure, decrease saturation,
scale to content, overlay photos,
duplicate photos, and zoom in.

Light scheme

Three lighting devices were used
for the shooting. The painting light was
located to the left of the model. The fill light
was near the optical axis of the camera.
Contrast – top behind the model.

Author's idea of photo №3. The idea of photo №3 "Temptation" was the birth of a new feeling, more earthly, in which sin transcends innocence.

Under the influence of Eros' powerful energy, Grace loses control of her mind and emotions. It seems that in a moment, and a thin veil will fall at the feet of the tempter. Eros acquires a clearer human, like image of a tamer of women's souls and hearts. His power becomes clearer – he seems to hypnotize his victim and absorb it completely – Love is doomed, it falls into the captivity of passion.

I was inspired to create this photo work by the unsurpassed images of Julia Margaret-Cameron, whose work dates back to the 60-70s of the 19th century, and which is still an ideal for many photographers. In the history of photography of that time, the search for new forms and styles began, which formed a new direction in photography – pictorialism. The similarity of painting is the main difference in this trend. Robert Demachy, Heinrich Kühn, Charles Puyo, Joan Vilatoba – this list can be endless. Indeed, all these masters were influenced by works of art from the Romantic era and such new styles as Art Nouveau, Jugendstil, and Pre-Raphaelite currents.

To create such an image, I used 2 photos that were collected in Adobe Photoshop and superimposed on each other. The shooting was carried out in the photo pavilion with the use of special equipment, and the restrained light image of the photo was the best solution to implement this idea.

Photo No. 4

**"Immersion in the Abyss" of the Master's Photo Art Project
"Erotica in Photography: from Analog to Digital"**

96

Camera / Lens

Canon 60D /
Helios 44-2 58 mm

Settings:

58 mm | F1.4 | ISO 100 | 1/25 s

**Image No. 4 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

Edit exposure, shadow, contrast
and saturation, blend brush, crop.

Light scheme

Filling light in front of the model.

Author's idea of photo №4. At the photo №4 “Immersion in the Abyss” we see the second of the three Graces – Beauty. Love is already captivated by the love of Eros, and she is still trying to fight in his nets. Her body curves are beginning to take on clearer images. We can't see her eyes yet, she hides them, but the path of temptation is inevitable.

The transparency of matter in this story is a kind of guide from the spiritual to the earthly, as well as a burden that will pull from heaven to the abyss.

This work also traces the influence of pictorialism, in particular the work of Joan Vilatoba, who also used translucent fabrics to enhance the artistic power of photography.

To create this image, I made my own Helios 44-2 58mm monocle lens. This lens was connected to a digital camera using an adapter and macro rings. This lens added the plasticity of the image and emphasized the plot.

Photo No. 5

**"Ghosts" of the Master's Photo Art Project
"Erotica in Photography: from Analog to Digital"**

98

Camera / Lens

Fujifilm XT-3 /
Fujinon XF 35 mm f/2.0

Settings:

35 mm | F3.2 | ISO 1600 | 1/250 s

**Image No. 5 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

Edit exposure, shadow, contrast
and saturation, crop, overlay photos,
zoom based on content.

Light scheme

Three lighting devices were used
for the shooting. The painting light was
located to the left of the model. The fill light
was near the optical axis of the camera.
Contrast – top behind the model.

Author's idea of photo №5. Numerous figures of Innocence appear before us in photo №5 "Ghosts". She is lost, confused in her thoughts, trying to escape from herself, but each time she returns to the same place. The walls of Eros' captivity rise every moment. Its purpose is to unite with the Graces in a whirlwind of feelings and temptations.

I was inspired to create this work by the work of André-Adolphe-Eugène Disdéri, who in the 60s of the 19th century was fond of creating collages and editing photos of actresses and ballerinas. In particular, he was mostly interested in slender female legs, which still attract modern viewers. Oscar Gustave Rejlander's work also did not leave me indifferent. Especially since he was the first photographer to present his work "Two Ways of Life" in 1857, which presented naked nature.

To create this photo, I used 6 photos that were compiled in Adobe Photoshop and superimposed on each other. The shooting was carried out in the photo pavilion using special equipment, and the chiaroscuro drawing of the image became the best solution for the realization of this idea.

Photo No. 6

**"Blues of Erotic Thoughts" of the Master's Photo Art Project
"Erotica in Photography: from Analog to Digital**

Camera / Lens

Fujifilm XT-3 /
Fujinon XF 35 mm f/2.0

Settings:

35 mm | F4 | ISO 800 | 1/125 s

**Image No. 6 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

Edit exposure, shadows, contrast
and saturation, blend brush, crop, stamp,
blend mode, zoom based on content.

Light scheme

Three lighting devices were used
for the shooting. The painting light was
located to the left of the model. The fill light
was near the optical axis of the camera.
Contrast – top behind the model.

Author's idea of photo №6. In photo №6 “Blues of Erotic Thoughts”, we see the already self-affirmed Eros, who has already fulfilled his purpose in the temptation of the Three Graces. Now he is satisfied with himself, enjoys his actions, rests and fantasizes about plans while Grace melts in his passion.

This work logically continues a series of previous photographs related to Pictorialism.

The photo contains two superimposed works. Also, the smoke is a complement to the plot of the picture, creating an atmosphere of dreaminess. The chiaroscuro nature of the lighting successfully emphasizes the idea of the plot.

Photo No. 7

**"Taste of Temptation" of the Master's Photo Art Project
"Erotica in Photography: from Analog to Digital**

Camera / Lens

Canon 60D /
Canon 24-105 f/4L IS II USM

Settings:

24 mm | F6.3 | ISO 500 | 1/40 s

**Image No. 7 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

Edit exposure, shadow, contrast
and saturation, blend brush, crop,
stamp, scale, content brush, restore
brush, adding stars and fog..

Light scheme

Three lighting devices were used
for the shooting. The painting light was
located to the left of the model. The fill light
was near the optical axis of the camera.
Contrast – top behind the model.

Author's idea of photo №7. Photo №7 "Taste of Temptation" depicts the celebration of Eros' victory. Graces are under his rule, perform whims and are able to do anything to satisfy their master. They are intoxicated by his sexual amusements and pastimes, unable to recover from love and passion yet. Their images and desires became concrete, human and sinful. A little more and they will fall. The future of Graces has already been determined by the shining stars drawing them into the abyss.

This work is characterized by the spirit of postmodernism. The combination of the mystical, the realistic and the domestic are characteristic of this trend.

The light and shadow nature of the lighting was used for this photo, which successfully emphasizes the details and the idea.

